

"PERFORMANCE OF PMFBY (PRADHAN MANTRI FASAL BIMA YOJANA) IN BARGARH DISTRICT OF ODISHA"S. Sahu^{*}, S. H. Kamble^{**}, R. D. Shelke^{***}, P. A. Bhosale^{****} and M. P. Bopche^{*****}¹ P. G. Scholar (Agri), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India² Associate Professor (Agricultural economics), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India³ Associate Professor (Agricultural economics), Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India⁴ P.G. Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India⁵ P.G. Scholar, Department of Agricultural Economics, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India,

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Abstract

Present study explored the effectiveness of the PMFBY scheme in Bargarh district of Odisha, assessed its benefit in stabilising farmer's income, and to know the operational barriers faced. The study employed primary data from 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers across twelve sample villages of four blocks comparing the efficiency of the scheme in managing agricultural risks. CAGR were used to evaluate the performance of PMFBY between 2016-17 to 2022-23, descriptive statistics was used for the investigation of income stability index of insured farmers and Garrett's ranking technique was used to evaluate constraints. The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Bargarh district of Odisha has shown potential in stabilizing farmers' income by providing compensation during agricultural losses, increasing mean gross income by 11 per cent and improving income stability from 0.67 to 0.74. The result shows a positive change in income stability of the insured farmers; However, the scheme faces several challenges, including declining participation during the kharif season, bureaucratic delays in claims processing, low farmer satisfaction, and inadequate complaint handling mechanisms. Additionally, the technical complexity of the application and settlement processes remains a significant hurdle.

Keywords: PMFBY, CAGR, income stability, indemnity

Introduction

The agriculture sector in India is a vital component of the country's economy, employing a significant portion of the population and contributing approximately 18.3 per cent to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) for the financial year 2022-23. It plays a crucial role in providing food security, supporting rural livelihoods and driving overall economic growth. The sector encompasses a diverse range of crops, including cereals (such as rice, wheat and maize), pulses, oilseeds, fruits, vegetables and cash crops like cotton and sugarcane (Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare). Small and marginal farmers constitute a significant portion of the farming community and the government has implemented various schemes and initiatives to improve their livelihoods and enhance agricultural productivity. Land reforms, credit facilities, subsidies and technological advancements have been some of the measures undertaken to support the agriculture sector.

Apart from being a major source of livelihood, agriculture also supplies raw materials to various industries, including textiles, food processing and agro-based industries. The sector faces challenges such as fragmented landholdings, water scarcity, market fluctuations and weather-related risks, which necessitate ongoing efforts to ensure sustainable growth and resilience in the agricultural sector.

Crop insurance is a critical component of India's agricultural sector, addressing the numerous challenges that farmers face in their pursuit of food production and livelihood. The Indian economy heavily relies on agriculture and a vast majority of the population is engaged in farming activities. However, farming is inherently risky due to its dependency on monsoons, which can be erratic and unpredictable. Natural disasters like droughts, floods, cyclones and pest infestations can lead to crop failures and substantial financial losses for farmers, often pushing them into a cycle of debt and poverty. Crop insurance serves as a safety net for farmers by providing financial assistance when they encounter crop losses due to adverse weather conditions or other covered risks. This helps them recover from the losses and continue their agricultural activities without being burdened by the financial setback.

Crop Insurance in India has come a long way since its inception; however, the policies have evolved with time to be more relevant for farmers. India has witnessed the evolution of crop insurance, from Comprehensive Crop Insurance Scheme (CCIS) in 1985 to National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS) in 1999 and Modified National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (MNAIS), that started in 2010-11. The launch of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in 2016 was a

landmark initiative that not only reduced premium rates but also introduced technology-based standards to ensure expedited claim settlements while enhancing the scope for coverage of loanee and non-loanee farmers (Yoga & Vetrivel, 2012)

In these series of reforms in PMFBY, the government has gone on to strengthen the use of technology by integrating real-time data from remote sensing, mobile apps and satellite imagery with measures that enhance accuracy in crop loss assessment process allowing seamless flow of compensations. Crucially, these initiatives help to buffer farmers against the uncertainties of agriculture at the same time as securing a more sustainable future for this sector.

The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) has shown significant improvements, particularly in premium structure. Farmers now pay only 2 per cent for kharif crops, 1.5 per cent for rabi crops, and 5 per cent for annual commercial and horticultural crops, with the government covering the rest. There's no cap on government subsidies, ensuring full compensation without premium capping, which previously reduced payouts. Technology, like smartphones for data collection and remote sensing, has streamlined claims and reduced crop-cutting experiments. Premiums are now delinked from past records, and insurance units are smaller, covering village-level risks. Direct bank transfers help speed up claim settlements and reduce corruption (Rathore and Rao, 2017).

The analysis of effects and progress helps in exploring PMFBY, which can help understand the socio-economic impact on farmers better. It is a very important proactive role in stabilizing the incomes of farmers, which would stop rural distress migration and farmer suicides due to financial that pressure. A review of the policy design, implementation and outcomes through research can help improve PMFBY for its sustainable future. Further, studying in what way the technology is being incorporated offers a telling perspective into how insurance systems can be turned more streamlined and inclusive.

Jamanal *et al.* (2019) conducted a study in Karnataka State during 2017-18 using an "Ex-post-facto" research design. The research focused on the districts of Belgavi, Dharwad, Haveri and Vijayapura, selected based on a higher number of insured farmers. From these districts, two taluks were chosen and within each taluk, three villages were randomly selected, resulting in a total of 24 villages. The study's sample comprised 240 respondents. Data were analysed using Garrett's Ranking Technique, which revealed that the primary constraint faced by insured farmers was the delay in receiving claims, with the highest Garrett Score (GS) of 73.53, ranking first. The second major issue was

inadequate compensation (GS-61.51, Rank-II), followed by officials' bias in loss assessment (GS-56.42, Rank-III). In terms of farmers' suggestions, the top recommendation was that claims should be disbursed before the start of the next season, receiving the highest Garrett Score of 75.70 and ranking first. The second suggestion was the establishment of a separate insurance cell at the Block/Taluk level (GS-66.40, Rank-II). The third suggestion highlighted the need for more training on Crop Insurance Schemes (GS-54.91, Rank-III).

Sharon *et al.* (2019) evaluated the growth performance of crop insurance schemes in India and Andhra Pradesh using data from the Agriculture Insurance Company of India. The study analysed the National Agricultural Insurance Scheme (NAIS), Weather-Based Crop Insurance Scheme (WBCIS), and Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), focusing on key indicators like the number of farmers insured, area insured, premiums, and claims paid. Nationally, NAIS showed moderate growth, with a 10.43 per cent increase in insured farmers and 13.93 per cent growth in the number of farmers benefitted. In contrast, WBCIS exhibited higher growth, with 50.48 per cent more farmers insured and 57.32 per cent more farmers benefitting. In Andhra Pradesh, NAIS recorded mixed results, with negative growth in area insured (-0.27 per cent) and claims paid (-17.85 per cent). However, WBCIS saw remarkable growth across all metrics, especially in the area insured (232.83 per cent) and claims paid (146.96 per cent), highlighting its superior performance compared to NAIS in the region. Kumar (2020) investigated the impact of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) in Raipur district, Chhattisgarh, revealing a 5.42 per cent increase in insured farmers from *kharif* 2016 to *kharif* 2018. The insured sum rose from ₹290.09 crores to ₹371.74 crores during this period. Farmers who participated in PMFBY reported higher yields and profits compared to those without insurance, indicating positive outcomes from the scheme.

Chadha and Srivastava (2022) evaluated the growth performance and variability of NAIS and WBCIS using secondary data. The analysis revealed that both schemes experienced growth across various metrics. For NAIS, the maximum growth rate and instability index for claims paid were 10.60 per cent and 79.62 per cent, respectively. Compound annual growth rates for the number of farmers insured, area insured, sum insured, gross premium, farmers' premium and number of farmers benefitted were 4.40 per cent, 3.81 per cent, 8.82 per cent, 9.50 per cent, 9.45 per cent and 5.83 per cent, respectively. For the WBCIS, significant growth was observed in the number of farmers benefitted (14.10 per cent) and in sum insured, farmers' premium and gross premium collected. The progress of the newly implemented PMFBY and RWBCIS was also analysed.

Rawat and Zechariah (2022) conducted a study in Faridabad district during 2021-2022 to evaluate various aspects of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). The research focused on understanding the socio-economic characteristics of farmers, their responses to PMFBY, its impact on both insured and uninsured farmers, the constraints in adopting the scheme and suggestions provided by respondents. Using an extensive random sampling process, the study concentrated on two blocks, Ballabgarh and Tigaon, known for their high numbers of Kisan Credit Card (KCC) loanee farmers who are automatically covered by PMFBY. Ten villages with the highest numbers of loanee and insured farmers were randomly selected and a total of 120 farmers—60 insured and 60 uninsured—were personally interviewed. The findings revealed that only 18 out of the 60 insured farmers were satisfied with PMFBY. Among the uninsured farmers, 56.67 per cent identified a lack of awareness as the main reason for not participating in the scheme.

Jiragal *et al.* (2023) conducted a study in Kolar district, Karnataka, during the 2021-22 period, examining the constraints and suggestions from both beneficiary and non-beneficiary farmers regarding the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). The study encompassed all five talukas in the district, with a sample consisting of 150 beneficiaries and 50 non-beneficiaries. The analysis identified several key constraints faced by beneficiaries in accessing PMFBY benefits.

The primary issue reported was delays in receiving claims, affecting 12.67 per cent of respondents. Inadequate compensation was the second most common issue, cited by 12 per cent of beneficiaries. Perceived bias in loss assessment and a lack of transparency from insurance companies, particularly regarding why some eligible farmers did not receive payments, were reported by 11.33 per cent of respondents. The complexity of banking procedures and formalities was also a significant constraint, mentioned by 10.67 per cent of beneficiaries. Additionally, 8.67 per cent of farmers highlighted poor awareness of PMFBY features and procedures, as well as issues with bank officials refusing to accept premiums due to outstanding loans, both ranked fifth. Regarding suggestions for improvement, the most favoured measure among beneficiaries was the timely payment of insurance claims, advocated by 14.67 per cent of respondents. The second most common suggestion, supported by 13.33 per cent, was reducing premium amounts for horticultural crops. Other significant suggestions (12.67 per cent) included disbursing claims before the start of the next season, establishing a dedicated PMFBY cell at the block level and increasing mass media or mobile SMS announcements. Providing insurance facilitation camps at the village level was supported by 12 per cent of respondents, while organizing more training sessions on PMFBY garnered 11.33 per cent support, ranking fifth.

Objectives

To examine the progress of PMFBY in Bargarh district
To analyse the impact of PMFBY on income stability of farmers
To identify the constraints in its implementation and suggestions thereof.

Materials And Methodology

A multistage purposive sampling technique was used for the selection of the district, talukas, villages and sample farmers. Bargarh district was purposively selected for the study based on maximum number of insured farmers. From the selected Bargarh district, four talukas were chosen based on the progress of PMFBY. Three villages were selected from each taluka based on the scheme's progress. From each selected villages, 10 farmers insured under the scheme and 10 non-insured farmers were randomly selected. Thus, a total of 120 insured farmers and 120 non-insured farmers under PMFBY were chosen for the present investigation.

The survey method was adopted for data collection. To obtain the required primary data a pre-tested schedule was prepared to obtain data from the selected farmers through personal interviews. Both primary and secondary data were collected for the present investigation. Primary data were collected from 120 insured and 120 non-insured farmers using a pre-tested schedule for the *kharif* season of 2023. Secondary data on the progress of PMFBY in the district were gathered from published sources (India stat, PMFBY websites) for the period from 2016 to 2023.

CAGR was employed to study the progress of PMFBY. The CAGR was estimated by using following formulas.

$$Y_1 = a.b^t \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Where,

Y = Dependent variable for which growth rate is to be estimated, t = Time variable, b = Regression coefficient, a = Intercept

This equation was estimated after transforming (1) as follows

$$\text{Log } y = \text{log } a + t \text{ Log } b \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Then the per cent compound growth rate (r) was computed using the relationship.

$$\text{CGR } (r) = [\text{Antilog } (\text{log } b) - 1] \times 100 \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

The significance of the regression coefficient was tested using the student's 't' test

Impact of PMFBY on stability of farm income were estimated by using descriptive statistics.

$$\text{Mean income} = \frac{\sum \text{income}}{N}$$

Where N is the number of observations.

$$\text{Standard Deviation} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (X - \text{Mean})^2}{N}}$$

The standard deviation measures the amount of variation or dispersion from the average income.

$$CV = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

This expresses the standard deviation as a percentage of the mean, indicating relative variability.

$$\text{Income stability index} = 1 - CV$$

The Income stability Index was a metric used to assess the stability of income within a population or region. Where: CV is the coefficient of variation.

Finally, the study used Garrett's Ranking Technique to rank various factors based on their perceived importance or severity, often applied in surveys where respondents rank their preferences or concerns.

The ranks were converted into Garrett scores using the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \left(\frac{R_{ij} - 0.5}{N_j} \right) \times 100$$

Where,

R_{ij} = Rank given for the i th factor by the j th individual

N_j = Number of factors ranked by the j th individual

Garrett's table was used to find the score corresponding to each percent position. The percentage position of each rank was converted into scores using Garrett's table. For each factor, the scores from all individuals were summed up and then divided by the total

number of farmers who provided scores. These average scores for each factor were then ranked in order and conclusions were drawn based on these rankings.

Results And Discussion

The study analysed the performance of PMFBY scheme with the help of CAGR. The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the number of farmers insured under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) is reported in Table 1. At the national level, the CAGR showed a decline of -7 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -2 per cent per annum for *rabi*, both significant at the 5 per cent level. This downward trend aligns with Chadha and Srivastava's (2022) findings from earlier schemes like the NAIS and WBCIS, indicating ongoing issues such as delayed claim settlements, low awareness, and declining farmer trust in PMFBY. Odisha reflected a negative CAGR of -2 per cent per annum per annum in *kharif* though positive 2 per cent per annum per annum in *rabi* and statistically significant at 5 per cent level. This implies that there was regional issue in the implementation of the scheme especially during the *kharif* season but displayed good results in the *rabi* season. In the current Bargarh district study, exceptional growth was evidenced with 7 per cent per annum CAGR in *kharif* and 12 per cent per annum in *rabi*, statistically significant at 5 per cent level. It provides evidence of positive deviations in farmer participation, fuelled by improved localized awareness and claim processing.

Table 1: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of number of insured farmers from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-7%**
		t value	-1.98
2	Odisha	CAGR	-2%**
		t value	-0.60
3	Bargarh	CAGR	7%
		t value	2.82

Note: **-Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the insured area under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across India, Odisha, and Bargarh is reported in Table 2.

In terms of overall insured area at the national level the CAGR for overall cultivation both in *kharif* and *rabi* season was 1 per cent per annum. This slow yet positive growth is in consonance with that observed by Chadha and Srivastava (2022) about the earlier schemes NAIS and WBCIS as awareness and complexity in claim processing hindered their growth. In Odisha, however, the area under the cultivator insured also deteriorated with a CAGR of -2 per cent per annum for both the seasons and being significant at a 5 per cent level. This points to intra-administrative shortcomings and low visibility, which, as Chadha and Srivastava noted earlier, characterise reduced participation in some areas. On the other hand, there was CAGR growth of 4 per cent in *kharif* and 8 per cent per annum in *rabi* both at 5 per cent level of significance in Bargarh district. This positive outcome reaffirms the argument of localized impacts such as in terms of fixed capital investments, reasons in administration and social mobilisation highlighted by Chadha and Srivastava (2022).

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the reported claims under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across India, Odisha, and Bargarh is reported in Table 3. The total number of reported claims at the national level was higher, with the CAGR for *kharif* being 8 per cent per annum and that for *rabi* 44

per cent per annum and it was statistically significant at a 5 per cent level. Chadha and Srivastava (2022) applied similar analysis and observed that claims for crop insurance increased, pointing to increased crop loss by poor climate and better claims management especially in *rabi* season. The moderate *kharif* growth could be due to ongoing problems with delayed processing or underreporting of claims.

The reported claims were lesser in Odisha; the CAGR was -56 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -44 per cent per annum for *rabi*, both at a 5 per cent level of significance. This could mean significant complications within the claims process, which may be related to bureaucracy and a lack of farmer confidence in the scheme. Chadha, and Srivastava (2022) highlighted that; similarly, the states with weak infrastructural and awareness faced such problems as Odisha which had severe systemic challenges to claim settlement.

There was also evidence of a decrease in reported claims in Bargarh district with CAGR of -29 per cent per annum in *kharif* season and -82 per cent per annum in *rabi* season both statistically significant at 5 per cent level. This results in state level data indicating severe problems in processing of claims as in Bargarh or *rabi* season which though has reported localized success stories in other regions. This can be attributed to delay in administrative procedures or lack of proper coordination between the insurers and the farmers, which has led to the overall loss of confidence in the scheme.

Table 2: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of area insured the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	1%**
		t value	0.51
2	Odisha	CAGR	-2%**
		t value	-0.59

3	Bargarh	CAGR	4%**	8%**
		t value	1.22	0.73

Note: **.-Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)

Table 3: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of reported claim the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	8%
		t value	44%**
2	Odisha	CAGR	-56%**
		t value	-44%**
3	Bargarh	CAGR	-29%**
		t value	-82%**

Note: (**). Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the approved claims under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across India, Odisha, and Bargarh is shown in Table 4.

Approved claims at the national level were sharply down, with a CAGR of -60 per cent per annum in *kharif* and -26 per cent per annum in *rabi*, both statistically significant at 5 per cent level. This decline underscores continuing struggles to settle claims with increasing reported claims. Like Chadha and Srivastava (2022), they emphasised administrative delays and inefficiencies which lead to low approval rates. For example, reported and approved claims have shown a gap that needs to be worked upon, especially in *kharif* which has resulted in high rejection or delay in registering claims and thereby not giving farmers timely compensation.

In Odisha, negative growth of -56 per cent for *kharif* and -44 per cent per annum for *rabi* were also significant at 5 per cent level both for

approved claims. Chadha and Srivastava (2022) note that the firm reflects persistent claims processing problems, compounded by bad infrastructure and low awareness. It shows the fall to be a significant one, as many farmers must have lost out on vital financial help at key moments of crop loss.

Alarming declines were also observed in Bargarh district with a -29 per cent per annum CAGR in *kharif* and a gigantic -82 per cent per annum in *rabi* which are significant at 5 per cent mark. The district managed participation and area growth somewhat better, yet most importantly the decline of approved claims indicates that administrative delays were also present. Chadha and Srivastava (2022) pointed out that even regions with a successful record suffered serious delays in claim settlement, eroding farmer confidence and financial security. The steep fall in *rabi* claims could also reflect the fact that claims process was complicated by seasonal factors.

Table 4: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of approved claim from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-60%**
		t value	-26%**
2	Odisha	CAGR	-56%**
		t value	-44%**
3	Bargarh	CAGR	-29%**
		t value	-82%**

Note: (**). Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the total claims paid under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across India, Odisha, and Bargarh is reported in Table 5.

Total claims paid at the national level showed negative CAGRs of -5 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -20 per cent per annum for *rabi*, which are significant at the 5 per cent level. This shows us that even with an increase in the number of claims filed, the amount disbursed to the farmers has shown a reduction over time. Some of the decline is steeper than the *rabi*, which may be a sign of greater difficulty with the post monsoon season, it could be owing to the difficulty of assessing crop damage, or the processing of claims.

Kharif and *rabi* CAGRs of -26 per cent per annum in *kharif* and -30 per cent per annum in *rabi* were also significant at the 5 per cent level

in Odisha. This phenomenal reduction to so apparent inefficiencies of the state in processing and settling claims is indicative of a serious problem within the nation. The discrepancy between claims filed and payments may have been exacerbated to make things worse for financially instable farmers in such a state as agriculture is quite fragile in the face of weather variability.

The decline in claims paid was pronounced in both *kharif* (-29 per cent per annum CAGR) and *rabi* (-82 per cent per annum CAGR) in Bargarh district that amounted significant at 5 per cent level. Despite having better participation in the scheme and larger insured areas, the drop in total claims paid, principally in *rabi*, suggests the process of providing compensation to farmers has been plagued by delays and difficulties.

Table 5: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of total claim paid from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>
1	India	CAGR	-5%**
		t value	-20%**
2	Odisha	CAGR	-26%**
		t value	-30%**
3	Bargarh	CAGR	-29%**
		t value	-82%**

Note: (**). Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)

The analysis of Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) for the total farmers benefitted under the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) across India, Odisha, and Bargarh is reported in Table 6. The number of farmers benefiting from the scheme has sharply declined

nationally at a CAGR of -6 per cent per annum for *kharif* and -19 per cent per annum for *rabi* also significant at the 5 per cent level. This shows there is significant loss of outreach associated with the scheme, especially in critical cultivation periods. This contradicts Chadha and

Srivastava's (2022) findings of positive growth on earlier schemes like NAIS and WBCIS that recorded CAGR of 5.83 per cent per annum and 6.65 per cent per annum respectively. This is unfavourable to the efficiency of the agricultural support program which could be because of the withdrawal of the government's role, lack of efficiency in the administration or a shift in the agricultural insurance environment. Odisha registered a drop in *kharif* benefits by CAGR of -37 per cent per annum and the CAGR increase in the *rabi* season was 1 per cent per annum. It indicates a vulnerability of the state during *kharif* season

and points to the need for more targeted interventions to stabilize farmer benefits in Odisha.

A strikingly contrasting trend came to the fore in Bargarh district. The *kharif* season showed a sharp decline in farmer beneficiaries (-24 per cent per annum CAGR) compared to the *rabi* season with robust growth at a 45 per cent per annum CAGR, which is very significant at the 5 per cent level. Based on this, it appears that locally based program efforts, administrative efficiency, or a slightly more favourable climatic condition in *rabi* may have been the cause for the efficacy of the program in Bargarh.

Table 6: Compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of total farmers benefitted from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Sr. No.	Particulars	<i>Kharif</i>	<i>Rabi</i>	
1	India	CAGR	-6%**	-19%**
		t value	-3.02	-2.41
2	Odisha	CAGR	-37%**	1%**
		t value	-3.38	0.28
3	Bargarh	CAGR	-24%**	45%**
		t value	-0.31	-0.50

Note: () Significant at 5 per cent level, t Table value (2.36)**

The analysis of gross yield with and without compensation provides a comprehensive view of how insurance compensation impacts agricultural production and income stability for insured farmers which is shown in Table 7.

The base line measure of yield without insurance support is the mean gross yield for insured farmers without compensation of ₹111,251.35. The mean gross yield is then raised to ₹123,439.68 when compensation is introduced. This significant increase of around ₹12,188.33 (or 11 per cent) shows that compensation leads to agricultural productivity. However, evidence of this improved farmers' capacity to recover from losses and sustain further increases in production suggests that the insurance is compensation that helps to recover from losses and to improve financial stability and risk management.

Comparing the gross yield without compensation standard deviation (₹35,143.12) shows the variation amongst the yield of farmers. That much variability implies inherent risk and variability in agricultural production when the farmers don't have a safety net with compensation. On the other hand, if we compensate the standard deviation is ₹31,138.31. One way this reduction in variability tells us is that compensation has helped enhance more consistent production levels. Compensation provides a third means of doing this by providing financial support during adverse conditions so that incomes are stabilized and the fluctuations experienced by farmers are reduced.

With a coefficient of variation (CV) of 0.33, gross income without compensation is a risky and variable measure compared to mean income. Relative variability is reduced to 0.26 CVs with the compensation. This lower CV reveals that compensation is an important measure in reducing risk and variability in agricultural production. Compensation reduces losses so farmers can have more stable incomes and income.

Without compensation the income stability index is 0.67 implying a certain level of income instability. When the compensation is introduced the income index increases up to 0.74. The increase captures a big improvement in income stability for farmers who are compensated. The higher income index indicates that compensation sufficiently reduces income fluctuation and improves farmers' stable and reliable financial conditions. Farmer's ability to manage their finances a bit more is allowed through this added stability, and the farmer can also go through the ups and downs of agricultural production.

Finally, the comparison of gross income without or with compensation has been demonstrated as astonishing advantages of insurance compensation for farmers. Increasing gross income increases income not only in amounts but also reduces the variability and noise of the income. These findings show that insurance compensation is an effective means of managing risk and enable farmers to achieve more stable production and more robust financial stability

Table 7: Gross income stability and income stability index of sample insured farmers from the period 2016-17 to 2022-23

Particulars	Gross income without compensation	Gross income with compensation
Mean	111251.35	123439.68
Standard Deviation	35143.12	31138.31
Coefficient of Covariation	0.33	0.26
Income stability Index	0.67	0.74

Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers which is reported in Table 8. The highest mean score (58.17) indicates that "Insufficient Compensation" is the most critical constraint. Farmers feel that the compensation provided by the PMFBY scheme is inadequate relative to the actual financial losses incurred due to crop damage. This reflects a significant gap between the compensation amounts and the farmers' perceived need, highlighting the necessity for a comprehensive review and potential adjustment of compensation levels to ensure they align with the severity of losses experienced.

The delay in receiving compensation was reported as a major constraint, with a high mean score of 56.83 reflecting its impact. The lag between the occurrence of crop damage and the disbursement of compensation causes financial distress and disrupts the farmers' ability

to manage and recover from losses effectively. This suggests a need for improving the efficiency of compensation processing to provide timely financial relief.

The assessment of crop damage, which influences the compensation process, was found to be delayed. The mean score (56.25) indicates that delays in evaluating the extent of crop damage significantly affect the overall compensation timeline. Addressing this issue involves streamlining and expediting the assessment procedures to ensure that compensation is based on timely and accurate damage evaluations.

The grievance redressal mechanism is perceived as ineffective, leading to unresolved complaints and dissatisfaction among farmers. The high mean score (56.17) for this constraint underscores the need for improving the grievance handling system, making it more responsive and capable of addressing and resolving farmers' concerns efficiently.

The cost of the insurance premium is seen as a significant burden for farmers. This constraint highlights concerns over the affordability of the scheme, with the mean score of 56 indicating that the premium rates are perceived as high relative to the benefits provided. Reassessing the premium structure or offering financial assistance could enhance the scheme's accessibility.

The complexity of banking procedures and formalities poses a barrier to accessing insurance benefits with a mean score of 49.08 ranked sixth. Farmers face challenges in navigating these procedures, which affects the efficiency of the insurance process. Simplifying banking procedures and reducing formalities are crucial for improving the overall experience for farmers.

Poor coordination between banks and farmers affects the smooth processing of insurance claims. The mean score (44.58) suggests that better communication and collaboration between these entities are needed to streamline the insurance process and enhance its effectiveness.

Administrative challenges and complex paperwork were identified as constraints that deter farmers from filing claims. The mean score (42.57) indicates that these difficulties are significant but not as critical as other constraints. Simplifying paperwork and administrative processes can reduce barriers to accessing insurance benefits.

Lack of awareness about which crops are covered under the PMFBY scheme is a constraint, though it is ranked lower compared to other issues with a mean score of 42.17. This suggests a need for better communication about the scope of coverage to ensure that farmers are fully informed about their insurance options.

General ignorance about the PMFBY scheme itself is the least significant constraint but still indicates a need for improved outreach (mean 38.33). Ensuring that farmers are aware of the scheme's existence and its benefits is essential for increasing participation and maximizing the scheme's impact.

The findings from this study highlighted several critical weaknesses in the implementation and operationalization of the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). These constraints, identified through the analysis of various studies and the mean rankings obtained from the respondents, underlined the pressing need for improvements to enhance the scheme's effectiveness and outreach.

The study revealed a significant level of ignorance about the PMFBY scheme, which ranked tenth among the identified constraints (Mean: 38.33). This finding was consistent with several studies (Goudappa *et al.*, 2012; Mani *et al.*, 2012; Nain *et al.*, 2017; Panigrahi *et al.*, 2019) that underscored the widespread lack of awareness and knowledge about crop insurance schemes among farmers. The low awareness severely hampered the scheme's penetration and effectiveness, as farmers remained uninformed about its benefits, coverage and processes. This gap in knowledge highlighted the urgent need for intensified awareness programs and educational initiatives to ensure that farmers were fully informed about the PMFBY.

The delay in the realization of compensation emerged as a significant constraint, ranking second (Mean: 56.83). This issue had been recurrent in multiple studies (Jamanal *et al.*, 2019; Mathur and Gupta, 2019; Darshan *et al.*, 2021), where delayed payments caused severe financial distress to farmers, especially in the face of crop failures. Timely disbursement of claims was critical to the financial stability of farmers and the recurrent delays undermined the very purpose of the insurance scheme, which was to provide timely financial relief. Addressing this issue would require systemic changes, including streamlined procedures and enhanced coordination among implementing agencies.

The grievance redressal mechanism under PMFBY was identified as another significant weakness, ranking fourth (Mean: 56.17). Several studies (Swain, 2015; Srinivasulu, 2018) highlighted the inadequacy of the current grievance redressal framework, which failed to address farmers' complaints efficiently and effectively. The lack of a robust mechanism left farmers with unresolved issues, further eroding their trust in the scheme. Strengthening the grievance redressal system by

making it more accessible, transparent and responsive was essential for improving the overall efficacy of PMFBY.

The delayed assessment of crop damage ranked third (Mean: 56.25) among the constraints. The timely and accurate assessment of crop losses was crucial for the appropriate disbursement of claims. Delays in this process, as reported in various studies (Panigrahi *et al.*, 2019; Tanwar *et al.*, 2020), not only postponed compensation but also raised questions about the reliability and transparency of the assessment procedures. Introducing more efficient and technology-driven assessment methods could significantly reduce these delays.

The premium rate under PMFBY, though ranked fifth (Mean: 56), remained a contentious issue among farmers. Studies by Mani *et al.* (2012) and Tanwar *et al.* (2020) pointed out that many farmers perceived the premium rates as high, especially in the context of the limited financial returns they received. While the scheme's design aimed to make insurance affordable, the perceived high cost continued to deter many farmers from enrolling. A reconsideration of premium rates, possibly with differentiated rates for different crops or regions, could make the scheme more appealing.

The most critical weakness identified was the issue of insufficient compensation, which ranked first (Mean: 58.17). This finding aligned with the conclusions drawn by studies such as those by Jamanal *et al.* (2019) and Parthiban and Anjugam (2023), which highlighted the dissatisfaction among farmers regarding the compensation amounts received under the scheme. Insufficient compensation failed to cover the actual losses incurred by farmers, leading to financial instability and discouraging continued participation in the scheme. Revisiting the compensation formula and ensuring that it adequately reflected the actual losses could address this critical issue.

The bureaucratic hurdles involved in the processing and paperwork associated with PMFBY, ranked eighth (Mean: 42.75), also presented a significant barrier to the scheme's success. Farmers often faced challenges in navigating the complex procedures, which could lead to delays and errors in claim submissions (Mani *et al.*, 2012; Jamanal *et al.*, 2019). Simplifying the documentation process and providing better support and guidance to farmers could alleviate this issue.

The banking procedures and formalities required for PMFBY, ranked sixth (Mean: 49.08), were also highlighted as a constraint. Studies (Nagesh *et al.*, 2022; Jiragal *et al.*, 2023) pointed out that cumbersome banking procedures deterred farmers from enrolling in the scheme or delayed their access to benefits. Streamlining these procedures and improving coordination between banks and farmers could enhance the scheme's accessibility.

Insufficient coordination between banks and farmers, ranked seventh (Mean: 44.58), further exacerbated the challenges faced by farmers under PMFBY. The lack of clear communication and coordination often led to misunderstandings, delays and errors in the implementation of the scheme. Strengthening the relationship between banks and farmers through better communication channels and dedicated support staff could significantly improve the scheme's implementation.

Lastly, ignorance about the specific crops covered under the PMFBY scheme ranked ninth (Mean: 42.17). This lack of information led to confusion and misinformed decisions by farmers regarding their insurance options (Sona and Muniraju, 2018). Ensuring that farmers were well-informed about the crops covered under the scheme was essential for its success.

The analysis of constraints impacting the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) reveals several critical issues affecting its effectiveness. The most significant constraint is "Insufficient Compensation," indicating that compensation levels are perceived as inadequate compared to the financial losses incurred by farmers. This is closely followed by "Delay in Realisation of Compensation" and "Delayed Assessment of Crop Damage," which exacerbate the financial strain on farmers by prolonging the wait for compensation. The "Ineffective Grievance Redressal Mechanism" further compounds this issue, as unresolved complaints hinder farmers' trust in the scheme.

Additional constraints include the "Rate of Farmer's Premium," which is seen as a financial burden and complex "Banking Procedures and Formalities," which impede efficient access to benefits. While issues such as "Difficulties in Processing and Paperwork" and "Ignorance About Crops Covered" are less critical, they still contribute to the overall inefficiency of the scheme. Addressing these constraints

through targeted reforms—such as improving compensation levels, expediting damage assessments, enhancing grievance redressal mechanisms and simplifying administrative processes will significantly improve the scheme's effectiveness and farmer satisfaction.

Table 8. Constraints in the adoption of PMFBY given by sample insured farmers

Sr No.	Constraints	Mean	Rank
1	Ignorance about PMFBY scheme	38.33	X
2	Delay in realisation of compensation	56.83	II
3	Ineffective grievance redressal mechanism.	56.17	IV
4	Difficulties in processing and paperwork	42.75	VIII
5	Banking procedures and formalities	49.08	VI
6	Delayed assessment of crop damage	56.25	III
7	Rate of farmer's premium	56	V
8	Insufficient compensation under PMFBY scheme	58.17	I
9	Ignorance about crops covered under the scheme	42.17	IX
10	Insufficient coordination between banks and farmers	44.58	VII

The suggestions provided by respondents to improve the Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), ranked by their frequency and percentage distribution is presented in Table 9. The most common suggestion, made by 76 respondents (63%), was to increase the sum insured to cover more crop losses, as the current coverage is insufficient for farmers' needs. Prompt payment of compensation was the second most cited recommendation, with 68 respondents (57%) emphasizing faster disbursement to help farmers recover quickly after crop failure. A reduction in premium rates was suggested by 64 respondents (53%), as high costs hinder participation, especially among small and marginal farmers. Better grievance handling and increased transparency were recommended by 57 respondents (48%) to improve trust and participation in the scheme. Regular reviews and

updates to the scheme were supported by 51 respondents (43%) to adapt to new agricultural challenges. The use of technology, such as satellite imaging and drones, to improve crop monitoring and assessment was favoured by 46 respondents (38%). Expanding the scheme to cover more crops and risks was also supported by 46 respondents (38%). Simplifying the application and claim settlement processes was proposed by 41 respondents (34%) to reduce complexity for farmers. Including non-traditional crops in the scheme was recommended by 36 respondents (30%), especially for horticultural crops that are currently excluded. Lastly, 31 respondents (26%) suggested increasing awareness through campaigns to educate farmers about the benefits and processes of PMFBY, ensuring better participation and implementation.

Table 9. Suggestions given by sample insured farmers

Sr. no.	Suggestions	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
1	Increase awareness through extensive campaigns	31	26%	X
2	Simplify application, claim and settlement processes	41	34%	VIII
3	Expand coverage to more crops, risks and farmers	46	38%	VII
4	Reduce premium rates for affordability	64	53%	III
5	Improve transparency and grievance redressal	57	48%	IV
6	Enhance sum insured for adequate loss coverage	76	63%	I
7	Leverage technology for crop monitoring	48	40%	VI
8	Ensure timely payouts for prompt recovery	68	57%	II
9	Consider inclusive coverage for nontraditional crops	36	30%	IX
10	Regularly review and revise the scheme to address	51	43%	V

The analysis of suggestions for improving PMFBY implementation in this study aligns with conclusions from previous research, such as Rawat and Zechariah's study in Faridabad district. The top recommendation in the current study is to increase the sum insured, supported by 63 per cent of participants. This mirrors findings from Faridabad, where insured farmers also criticized the existing insurance and payout system and advocated for more transparent and adequate compensation. Both studies highlight that insufficient insurance protection undermines the farmers' ability to cope with risks, especially in areas with unpredictable climate conditions like Odisha and Haryana.

Timely payouts, supported by 57 per cent of respondents in this study, were also a major concern in Faridabad. Delayed payments are a recurring issue in PMFBY studies, as farmers need immediate compensation after crop losses. While both groups of farmers recommended simplifying the payout process, 40 per cent of Bargarh farmers showed growing interest in adopting real-time data monitoring

technology to improve the process. Reducing premium rates was another significant recommendation, with 53 per cent of respondents in Bargarh calling for lower costs, like 70 per cent of respondents in Faridabad. High premiums are recognized as a barrier for smallholder and marginal farmers across regions. In terms of procedural issues, 34 per cent of respondents in Bargarh called for simplifying the application and claim process, compared to 73 per cent in Faridabad. This suggests that while the need for simplification is clear, the urgency may vary by region. Awareness of the scheme was a lower priority in Bargarh, with only 26 per cent calling for better outreach compared to 73 per cent in Faridabad. This may indicate some improvement in awareness in Odisha, though further efforts are still needed.

The following policy recommendations are recommended to enhance the efficiency of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY). First, increasing the sum insured by increasing compensation caps would fill the existing disparities in the current limits and enhance the financial position of farmers. Pays more attention to the early payback so that

farmers can be protected in case of crop failure and their revenues be made steady. Ensuring that premium rates are lowered is always a goal if the scheme has to be popular then the rates should be slashed. Higher transparency and better grievance redressal mechanism would help creating that trust and address all the concerns that farmers have regarding this sector. It will also reduce clutter, increasing application, claim, and settlement ease and effectiveness.

Conclusions

The Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY) has demonstrated both strengths and significant challenges in its implementation in Bargarh district of Odisha. The scheme has shown promise in stabilizing farmers' income by providing compensation during times of agricultural loss, evidenced by improvements in income stability and reduced income variability for insured farmers. Compensatory payment from this scheme has enhanced the potential of stabilizing farmers income by paying the farmer during a loss-making season. By compensation, mean gross income of farmers increases of 11 percent though it showed that insurance help in reducing financial risk with the increase of index of income stability from 0.67 to 0.74. But it also pointed out a few research issues that need to be addressed. The Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) analysis exposed adverse skewed tendency of decaying participation in the scheme during the kharif season both at the state and national levels and upgraded tendency in Bargarh district during the rabi season.

The study also highlighted the bureaucratic problems that the actors encountered throughout the claims handling cycle, for example, lengthy response and provision of claims, which caused dissatisfaction and lack of confidence from farmers. Some of them include low remuneration, long waiting for reimbursement and poor complaint handling mechanisms which do not allow the scheme to afford the requisite financial support in time. However, the technical sophistication of the application and settlement processes remain a key problem.

To improve the effectiveness of PMFBY, the study suggests several policy recommendations: boosting the amount of cover towards loss causing events, improving bureaucratic formalities and delays, and stepped-up sensitization and popularization of the scheme among farmers. Another area of reform that would involve efficient use of technology in crop monitoring, as well as in expeditious and satisfactory resolutions of claims, is also another area of reform. In conclusion, while PMFBY holds the potential to transform the agricultural insurance landscape in India, particularly in districts like Bargarh, addressing its operational challenges is essential for building farmer trust and ensuring long-term sustainability.

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